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The Human Capital and Research Index at a global level

Decreased on average by 0.52% for the countries considered between 2013 and 2022

The "Human Capital and Research Index" is a measure that reflects the quality and level of human resources and research activities in a specific context, such as a country, region, or organization. This index takes into account factors related to education, training, knowledge, and innovation, which are essential for supporting economic growth and social development. Human capital refers to the skills, knowledge, experience, and abilities acquired by individuals through education and training. A population with a high level of human capital is capable of generating economic and social value thanks to its ability to innovate, work effectively, and adapt to market changes. Investments in education, training, and skill development are therefore crucial for strengthening human capital. The research aspect concerns scientific, technological, and innovative activities. The index considers the quality and quantity of research produced, the capacity for innovation, as well as the presence of research infrastructures and centers of excellence. A context where research is well developed tends to attract investments, create new technologies, and enhance global competitiveness. In summary, the "Human Capital and Research Index" is a complex indicator that evaluates the effectiveness of education and research in a specific context, highlighting the potential for sustainable growth and innovative development in that society.

Human Capital and Research Index in 2022. The Human Capital and Research Index for 2022 provides a significant overview of the level of intellectual, technological, and innovative development across various countries worldwide. This index, which considers factors such as education, research quality, innovation infrastructure, and the capacity to develop and apply new technologies, clearly shows how nations are differently positioned in terms of global competitiveness. At the top of the ranking, we find South Korea with a score of 66.4, followed by Germany (64.1) and Sweden (62.6). These countries demonstrate a strong synergy between education, research, and innovation. South Korea, for instance, has heavily invested in education and scientific research over recent decades, becoming a global leader in technological production and in the ability to transform knowledge into high-value-added products. Germany, with its long tradition of engineering and academic excellence, continues to be a benchmark for applied research and industrial innovation. Sweden and Switzerland, with scores of 62.6 and 62.4 respectively, are also examples of advanced economies that heavily invest in human capital and research, promoting a highly favorable environment for scientific and technological creativity. Moving further down the list, Australia (61.7), the United Kingdom (61.5), and Singapore (61.5) are other nations that have capitalized on advanced educational policies and research development strategies to maintain their global competitiveness. Singapore, in particular, represents an interesting case of a small nation that, despite lacking natural resources, has built a knowledge-based economy thanks to a high-quality education system and a favorable environment for innovation. The United Kingdom and Australia, on the other hand, combine centuries-old academic traditions with a well-developed research sector closely linked to industry. The United States, with a score of 59.9, remains one of the global powers in terms of research and development, although internal challenges such as inequality in access to education and the fragmentation of the educational system can negatively impact the overall index. However, the country remains a world leader in patent production and the ability to attract talent from around the world thanks to world-renowned universities and a dynamic startup and innovation ecosystem. Scandinavian countries like

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Finland (60.6) and Denmark (59.4), along with other European nations such as Austria (58.8) and the Netherlands (57.4), stand out for their strong support for welfare policies and inclusive education, which ensure a highly skilled workforce and a favorable environment for research. Finland is emblematic: despite a relatively small population, the country has built one of the best education systems in the world, emphasizing critical thinking and creativity, essential elements for research and innovation. Among emerging countries, China (53.1) and Japan (52.7) occupy prominent positions, albeit with significant differences. China has made great strides in the past decade, investing heavily in research and education with the goal of becoming a global technology leader. However, its system remains highly centralized and faces issues related to inefficiency and a lack of academic freedom. Japan, although a pioneer in many technological fields, seems to suffer from stagnation, with a rigid educational system and declining demographics posing significant challenges. Looking further down the ranking, we find Southern European countries like Italy (46.9), Spain (47.7), and Greece (45.4), which, despite having long academic traditions, suffer from structural problems related to ineffective resource management, youth unemployment, and a low capacity to retain talent. These factors limit their ability to compete with Northern European nations, where research is better integrated into the economic and social fabric. Russia (47) occupies a middle position, reflecting a still high research potential but hampered by a politically and economically unstable context that limits attractiveness for researchers and the capacity to innovate. Israel (48.1), on the other hand, is an example of how a small country can leverage its innovative strength thanks to a highly dynamic startup ecosystem and a research culture strongly oriented towards practical application and security. Eastern European nations, such as Poland (42.5), Hungary (41.3), and the Czech Republic (43.3), while having made significant progress in recent decades, still face substantial challenges in terms of modernizing their educational systems and integrating with global research markets. Southeast Asian countries like India (38.3), Malaysia (41), and Vietnam (27.2) are in a phase of rapid development, striving to close the gap with more advanced economies. However, the index reflects how the quality of education and access to research resources remain uneven, with stark disparities between urban and rural areas. Sub-Saharan African and South Asian nations occupy the lowest positions in the ranking, with scores below 20 points, such as Nigeria (17.4), Ethiopia (8.8), and Bangladesh (10.8). These countries are severely constrained by structural factors such as widespread poverty, inadequate educational systems, and limited capacity to invest in research and development. The lack of infrastructure, political stability, and financial resources makes it extremely difficult for these nations to build competitive human capital and support high-level research activities. However, in some contexts, signs of improvement are visible thanks to international support initiatives and the growth of emerging technological sectors, particularly in large urban centers. In conclusion, the 2022 Human Capital and Research Index shows a world still deeply divided in terms of the ability to enhance education, research, and innovation. While more advanced economies continue to dominate thanks to forward-looking policies and sustainable investments, many emerging and developing countries struggle to keep up. Nevertheless, global technological progress offers opportunities even for the most disadvantaged countries, provided they can overcome the structural challenges holding them back. This index highlights the crucial importance of investing in human capital and research as fundamental factors to ensure sustainable economic growth and social well-being in an increasingly competitive and interconnected world.

Human Capital and Research Index between 2013 and 2022. The Human Capital and Research Index (HCRI) is a key measure for evaluating a country's level of investment in human capital and scientific research. The analysis of data from 2013 to 2022 shows contrasting trends, with some nations recording significant improvements, while others experience a concerning decline. Among the countries that have shown a notable increase in the HCRI, Zambia (+117.65%), Pakistan (+107.79%), and Zimbabwe (+78.51%) are at the top of the list. These countries, often classified as emerging economies, have evidently made significant investments in human capital and research, an essential move to improve their global competitiveness. The growth in Zambia and Zimbabwe may reflect

government policies aimed at expanding education and research as tools for economic development. Similarly, India (+76.50%) and Peru (+76.08%) represent examples of rapidly growing economies that recognize the importance of investing in human capital to support innovation and technological development. India's growth, in particular, aligns with its strategy of becoming a global hub for technology and research, supported by a growing number of research institutes and a skilled workforce. Among the countries with moderate increases, China (+30.79%) and Turkey (+30.54%) stand out. These increases reflect the efforts of these countries to improve their research ecosystem, although they were already starting from a higher base compared to many other emerging countries. Developed nations such as Germany (+18.05%) and Canada (+16.80%) also show continuous improvements, indicating their sustained focus on investing in human capital and research to maintain their status as advanced and competitive economies. On the other hand, some countries show very limited growth or stagnation. For example, countries like Austria (+0.17%), Sweden (+0.16%), and Benin (0.00%) have registered minimal increases, while nations like Iran, Jamaica, and New Zealand have seen no change in the HCRI. These figures may indicate a maturity in the research and development system in these countries, or a lack of additional investments that could push the sector to new levels. It is alarming to observe that many countries have seen a significant decline in the human capital and research index. Among the most severe cases are Iceland (-25.04%), Armenia (-30.16%), Montenegro (-31.05%), and Uganda (-42.54%). The reduction in the HCRI in these countries could be due to various factors, including economic instability, political crises, or a decrease in investments in education and research. For example, Armenia and Montenegro, which have seen a considerable drop, may have been affected by economic constraints or a reduction in government priorities in these sectors. Uganda and Yemen, which recorded declines of 42.54% and 42.64%, respectively, highlight how internal conflicts and political instability can have devastating effects on investments in human capital and research. These data reflect the importance of continuous and strategic investment in human capital and research to support economic growth and innovation. Countries that consistently invest in these areas tend to see long-term benefits in terms of technological development and global competitiveness. However, where such investments are neglected, a decline is observed that can have long-term consequences on the ability to innovate and remain competitive. Moreover, the decline in many countries could be linked to external factors such as global economic crises, which reduce budgets allocated to education and research. In a world increasingly dominated by innovation and technology, human capital and research are fundamental to the resilience and growth of economies. Countries with stable or declining performance in these areas risk falling behind in global competition, with negative effects on future economic opportunities. In conclusion, the data related to the Human Capital and Research Index for the period 2013-2022 present a varied picture, with some nations making significant progress and others struggling to keep pace or even regressing. Countries that have strategically invested in human capital are reaping the rewards in terms of greater innovative capacity and economic growth. On the other hand, nations experiencing a decline need to consider new strategies to reverse the trend and ensure that investment in human capital and research remains a priority.

Economic Policies to Develop the Human Capital and Research Index. Developing the Human Capital and Research Index requires a set of integrated economic policies aimed at improving education, training, innovation, and a country's research capacity. Investing in a high-quality education system is the first step in developing human capital. It is essential to finance and improve access to all levels of education, from primary school to university. This includes adopting updated curricula that meet the needs of the labor market and technological innovation. Promoting the teaching of STEM subjects (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) is particularly important to prepare a workforce capable of contributing to technological and scientific development. Beyond formal education, it is crucial to invest in vocational and continuous training. Reskilling and upskilling programs help keep the workforce competitive and adaptable to technological changes. Policies that encourage collaboration between educational institutions, businesses, and universities

can ensure that the skills developed align with market needs. Increasing investments in research and development is essential to improve the Human Capital and Research Index. Economic policies should include tax incentives for companies investing in R&D, as well as direct funding for innovative projects. Creating public funds to finance research projects, both in universities and businesses, can stimulate innovation and lead to the development of new technologies. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) are crucial for creating synergies between the public sector, businesses, and universities. Such collaborations can facilitate resource sharing, improve efficiency, and ensure that research projects are aligned with market needs. Finally, it is important to create innovation ecosystems through the development of technology parks, start-up incubators, and industrial clusters that can attract talent and foster the growth of new high-value-added sectors. Supporting researcher mobility and promoting international collaborations is another key aspect to expand local knowledge and skills. Policies aimed at encouraging the return of skilled professionals can also help counter brain drain. These strategies, combined with a long-term vision focused on innovation and enhancing human resources, can ensure lasting improvement in the Human Capital and Research Index.

Conclusions. The value of the Human Capital and Research Index decreased by an average of 0.52% for the countries considered between 2013 and 2022. There are countries where this indicator grew significantly, such as Zambia with +117.65%, Pakistan with +107.79%, Zimbabwe with +78.51%, India with +76.50%, and Peru with +76.08%. However, there are also countries where the Human Capital and Research Index decreased much more than the average, such as Sri Lanka with -31.98%, Trinidad and Tobago with -33.62%, Uganda with -42.54%, Yemen with -42.64%, and Guinea with -50.00%.

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